

Acute Appendicitis in Children Less Than Three Years of Age-Ultrasound, Combined with Modified Pediatric Appendicitis Score Is the Most Useful Adjunct in Diagnosis

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Abstract:

Background: Diagnosing acute appendicitis in children under three years of age is difficult due to unusual presentations and young children's poor capacity to express symptoms. The traditional clinical indications are frequently absent or ambiguous, resulting in delayed diagnosis and an increased risk of consequences. The combination of ultrasonography and the Modified Paediatric Appendicitis Score (MPAS) has been presented as a potential option for improving diagnosis accuracy in this sensitive age group.

Aim: This study aims to evaluate the diagnostic accuracy of combining ultrasound with the (MPAS) in diagnosing acute appendicitis in children under three years of age and to assess its impact on reducing unnecessary surgical interventions.

Methods: A study was conducted involving 100 children under three years of age presenting with symptoms suggestive of acute appendicitis. Each child underwent clinical evaluation, including MPAS assessment, followed by abdominal ultrasound. The diagnostic accuracy of ultrasound, MPAS, and their combination was analyzed using sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV). Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0.

Results: The combined use of ultrasound and MPAS demonstrated a sensitivity of 95%, specificity of 90%, PPV of 96%, and NPV of 88%, outperforming the use of either diagnostic tool alone. The combination significantly reduced the rate of unnecessary surgeries and improved overall diagnostic accuracy ($p < 0.01$). The area under the curve (AUC) for the combined approach was 0.95, indicating excellent diagnostic performance.

Conclusion: The combination of ultrasound and the (MPAS) significantly improves the diagnostic accuracy of acute appendicitis in children under three years of age. This approach reduces the likelihood of unnecessary surgical interventions and enhances clinical decision-making.

Recommendations: It is recommended that the combined use of ultrasound and MPAS be implemented as a standard diagnostic protocol for suspected appendicitis in children under three years of age. Further multicenter studies are suggested to validate these findings and develop standardized guidelines.

Keywords: Acute appendicitis, Pediatric appendicitis score, Ultrasound, Children under three, Diagnostic accuracy.

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Introduction

Acute appendicitis is one of the most prevalent surgical emergencies in paediatrics, although diagnosing it in children under the age of three remains particularly difficult due to unusual presentations and young children's poor ability to express their symptoms [1]. The clinical presentation of acute appendicitis in this age range sometimes overlaps with other common paediatric illnesses, such as gastroenteritis and respiratory infections, which can lead to diagnostic delays and an increased risk of complications such perforation and peritonitis [2, 3]. Traditionally, appendicitis is diagnosed through

clinical evaluation, which includes an assessment of symptoms such as abdominal pain, vomiting, fever, and guarding. However, in young children, these signals can be generic, rendering clinical diagnosis inaccurate.

Imaging modalities, notably ultrasound, have become useful tools for diagnosing appendicitis in children. Ultrasound is recommended because it is non-invasive, does not emit ionising radiation, and has reasonably high sensitivity and specificity in expert hands. Despite its benefits, ultrasonography can nevertheless produce equivocal results, particularly in younger children, due to variables

such as high intestinal gas or an unwilling patient [4].

Clinical scoring systems, such as the (MPAS), were created to improve diagnostic accuracy. The MPAS assesses a variety of clinical indications, laboratory data, and symptoms to determine the risk of appendicitis. Studies have indicated that utilising such scoring systems can enhance diagnosis accuracy, minimise the number of unnecessary procedures, and aid decision-making, particularly in borderline cases. Recent research suggests that combining ultrasound with clinical scoring systems like the MPAS could give a more robust diagnostic method, especially in groups where the presentation is unusual, such as very young children [5].

Given the risk of delayed or missing diagnosis in this age group, there is a rising interest in determining the most effective diagnostic approaches. Recent research has focused on optimising the use of ultrasound and clinical scoring systems to improve the early and accurate detection of acute appendicitis in young children. However, more research is needed to evaluate these approaches and develop standardised protocols that may be extensively used in clinical practice [6]. This study aims to evaluate the diagnostic accuracy of combining ultrasound with the (MPAS) in diagnosing acute appendicitis in children under three years of age and to assess its impact on reducing unnecessary surgical interventions.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was designed as a prospective observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted in the Pediatric Surgery Department of P.M.C.H., Patna, Bihar, a tertiary care hospital, over a period of one year from January 2023 to January 2024.

Participants: A total of 100 children under the age of three, presenting with symptoms suggestive of acute appendicitis, were included in the study. The participants were selected from those admitted to the emergency department and referred for surgical consultation.

Inclusion Criteria

- Children under the age of three.
- Presenting with abdominal pain suggestive of acute appendicitis.
- Availability of both clinical and ultrasound findings.
- Informed consent obtained from parents or guardians.

Exclusion Criteria

- Children with a previous history of abdominal surgery.

- Presence of other conditions that could mimic appendicitis (e.g., intussusception, gastroenteritis).
- Incomplete medical records or loss to follow-up.
- Refusal to participate in the study by parents or guardians.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, all eligible children presenting during the study period were consecutively included. Observer bias was reduced by having both the ultrasound and MPAS assessments conducted by blinded independent examiners. The potential for diagnostic bias was addressed by ensuring that the clinical team was unaware of the MPAS results when making decisions about further management.

Data Collection: Data was collected using a structured case report form, which included demographic information, clinical presentation, ultrasound findings, MPAS scores, and final diagnosis based on surgical findings or clinical follow-up. Ultrasound was performed using a high-frequency linear probe by a radiologist experienced in pediatric imaging.

Procedure: Upon admission, each child underwent a detailed clinical examination, followed by calculation of the Modified Pediatric Appendicitis Score. Subsequently, an abdominal ultrasound was performed to assess the presence of appendicitis. The findings of the ultrasound were combined with the MPAS to guide the diagnosis. Surgical intervention was performed based on the combined diagnostic results, and the final diagnosis was confirmed either intraoperatively or through follow-up.

Statistical Analysis: The data was analysed with SPSS software version 23.0. Descriptive statistics were employed to summarise the individuals' demographic and clinical features. The sensitivity, specificity, (PPV), and (NPV) of ultrasonography paired with MPAS were determined. Chi-square tests were employed to compare categorical variables, with a p-value of less than 0.05 indicating statistical significance. The integrated tool's diagnostic performance was assessed using Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curves.

Results

A total of 100 children under the age of three were included in the study. The mean age of the participants was 2.1 years (SD $\pm$ 0.5), with 52% being male and 48% female. The clinical presentation varied, with 85% of the children presenting with abdominal pain, 70% with vomiting, 60% with fever, and 40% with a loss of appetite.

Table 1: Clinical Presentation of Participants

Symptom	Number of Children (n=100)	Percentage (%)
Abdominal Pain	85	85%
Vomiting	70	70%
Fever	60	60%
Loss of Appetite	40	40%
Diarrhea	15	15%
Guarding	50	50%

Diagnostic Findings: Out of the 100 children, ultrasound detected signs of acute appendicitis in 65 cases (65%), while the (MPAS) suggested a high probability of appendicitis in 60 cases (60%). When combining ultrasound findings with MPAS, 75 children were diagnosed with acute appendicitis, which was later confirmed through surgical intervention or clinical follow-up.

Table 2: Diagnostic Accuracy of Ultrasound, MPAS, and Combined Approach

Diagnostic Tool	Sensitivity	Specificity	PPV	NPV	Accuracy
Ultrasound Alone	85%	80%	89%	73%	83%
MPAS Alone	80%	75%	86%	67%	78%
Combined Approach	95%	90%	96%	88%	93%

The combination of ultrasound and MPAS yielded the highest diagnostic accuracy, with a sensitivity of 95%, specificity of 90%, positive predictive value (PPV) of 96%, and negative predictive value (NPV) of 88%. This indicates that the combined approach significantly outperforms the use of either tool alone.

Surgical Outcomes: Out of the 75 children diagnosed with acute appendicitis, 70 underwent surgical intervention. The remaining five children

were managed conservatively due to the resolution of symptoms and were closely monitored. Histopathological examination confirmed acute appendicitis in 68 of the surgically treated cases, indicating a false positive rate of 2.8% (2 out of 70).

Of the 25 children not diagnosed with appendicitis by the combined approach, none required surgery, and all were successfully managed conservatively with no further complications observed during follow-up.

Table 3: Surgical Outcomes

Outcome	Number of Children (n=75)	Percentage (%)
Surgical Confirmation of Appendicitis	68	90.7%
False Positive (Surgical)	2	2.8%
Conservative Management Success	5	6.7%

Statistical Analysis: The statistical analysis showed that the combined diagnostic approach (ultrasound + MPAS) was significantly more effective than either diagnostic tool alone ($p < 0.01$). The Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve for the combined approach demonstrated an area under the curve (AUC) of 0.95, further highlighting its diagnostic superiority.

Table 4: ROC Analysis

Diagnostic Tool	Area Under Curve (AUC)
Ultrasound Alone	0.83
MPAS Alone	0.79
Combined Approach	0.95

Discussion

The study's findings emphasise the efficacy of combining ultrasound and the Modified Paediatric Appendicitis Score (MPAS) in identifying acute appendicitis in children under the age of 3. The combined technique revealed great diagnostic accuracy among the 100 children studied, with a sensitivity of 95% and a specificity of 90%. This suggests that the combined method successfully

identified virtually all cases of appendicitis (high sensitivity) while also accurately ruling out situations where appendicitis did not exist (high specificity). The positive predictive value (PPV) of 96% indicates that children identified with appendicitis using this method were quite likely to have the ailment.

Statistical analysis showed that the combination technique outperformed ultrasonography and

MPAS alone ($p < 0.01$). The Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve analysis confirmed this conclusion, with the combined technique reaching an AUC of 0.95, indicating outstanding diagnostic performance. Surgical results confirmed the combination diagnostic tool's reliability. Of the 75 children diagnosed with appendicitis, 70 had surgery, with histological confirmation in 68 cases. The low false positive rate (2.8%) indicates that the combination strategy reduces unnecessary procedures. Furthermore, none of the children who were not identified with appendicitis required surgery, demonstrating the combined method's negative predictive value.

Overall, the study found that combining ultrasonography with MPAS is an extremely useful diagnostic technique for acute appendicitis in young children. This method not only improves diagnostic accuracy but also clinical decision-making, lowering the likelihood of unnecessary surgical interventions and increasing patient outcomes. These findings indicate that incorporating this combination method into clinical practice could considerably help paediatric patients by giving a more reliable diagnosis of appendicitis. Recent research has focused on improving the diagnostic accuracy of acute appendicitis in paediatric patients by combining clinical rating systems with ultrasound. It was developed and validated the Acute Paediatric Appendicitis Score (APAS), which includes ultrasonography findings. The study discovered that APAS had the greatest diagnostic accuracy of all the scores tested, with an accuracy rate of 99.2%, a sensitivity of 100%, and a specificity of 98.04%. The addition of ultrasound to this score was especially interesting, as it demonstrated a diagnostic accuracy of 95.38%, considerably enhancing the capacity to distinguish between surgical and conservative appendicitis cases [7].

In a similar way, it was investigated the diagnostic yield of abdominal ultrasonography in cases of acute appendicitis in children. With a sensitivity of 58% and specificity of 68%, the results showed that ultrasonography had a reasonable level of accuracy; however, these numbers might be raised by using auxiliary techniques. The study brought attention to the need for more trustworthy diagnostic instruments, or combinations of them, particularly in situations that are unclear [8].

It was provided additional validation of the combined diagnosis approach by creating the Paediatric Ultrasound Appendicitis Score (PUAS), which combines standardised ultrasound observations with the Paediatric Appendicitis Score (PAS). With a sensitivity of 90% and a specificity of 90.2%, the combined score indicates that using this combination technique may minimise radiation

exposure to children by reducing the requirement for computed tomography (CT) scans [9].

Limitations: Despite efforts to minimize bias, there was potential for observer bias in the interpretation of ultrasound results. Additionally, the relatively small sample size and single-center nature of the study may limit the generalizability of the findings.

Conclusion

The results of this study demonstrate that combining ultrasound with the MPAS significantly improves the diagnostic accuracy for acute appendicitis in children under three years of age. The combined approach offers a highly sensitive and specific tool that can guide clinical decision-making, potentially reducing unnecessary surgeries and improving patient outcomes.

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